

Theory of Age Periods of Personality Development

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Abstract: In this article: In the study of the theory of personality development of young periods, the American psychologist E. Erikson divides personality development into 8 periods and each of them has its own unique characteristics, and E. Spranger includes the period of adolescence from 13 to 19 years of age for girls and from 14 to 22 years of age for boys. the main changes that occur in this age period are recommended.

Keywords: love, youth, discovery of personal "I", growth of reflection, psyche, personality development, sensorimotor intelligence, improvement in ontogenesis, youth, role delay, adolescent, teenager.

Introduction

If a person is not one of them, then he is not one of them, if he is not one of them, then he is not one of them, if he is not one of them, then he is not one of them, if he is not one of them, then he is not one of them. Every person living in this world has a unique connection between humanity, culture and acceptance, as well as normal social behavior, which manifests itself in every movement. Psychology is the study of a number of individuals and communities who communicate with each other through the study of human nature, the development and improvement of English legitimacy. Abu Nasr Farobiy, A.Navoi Ibn Sina, outside of the yuzlab, the East was known as a philosophical and social circle of people who studied the works of bagishlaganlar. At the same time, as in the case of English, it should be similar to English and should be similar to English. He is also one of the oldest and oldest religious figures in the world. He is one of the oldest and oldest religious figures in the world. He is also one of the oldest and oldest religious figures in the world. He is also one of the oldest and oldest religious figures in the world. He is also one of the oldest and oldest religious figures in the world. He is also one of the oldest and oldest religious figures in the world. He is also one of the oldest and oldest religious figures in the world.

The theory that analyzes personality behavior with the help of emosia, miles and the like, which are irrational (except mental cognitive processes) components of the psyche, is called psychodynamics. One of the major manifestations of this theory is the American psychologist E.It's Erickson. He divides the development of personality into 8 periods, and each of them has its own unique character.

The first period is infancy. During this period, the baby develops a feeling of "confidence" in the external world, which laid the foundation for unconsciousness. The chief causative agent of Bu is the target of the parents ' affection, care and diligence. If a baby does not have

a base of trust, but a feeling of distrust of being, it is likely that a reflective danger will arise in the form of limitation, frustration in people who have grown up in taq-dir.

In the second period, that is, in early childhood, a feeling of semi-independence and personal dignity is formed in the creature, or, on the contrary, a feeling of shame and doubt is formed, which is their opposite. The growth of independence in a child, creating a wide opportunity to control his own body, carefully sets the stage for the formation of feelings of order and discipline, responsibility, responsibility, respect, which become personality traits in his future.

The third period covers children aged 5 to 7 years. During this period, there is a sense of initiative, a desire to do and do something. In this case, the child will feel guilty if there is no "opportunity to do the will" in him. At this young age, processes such as a "round table," group play, communication with peers become of great importance, which allows the child to try various roles and grow in imagination. At the same time, the child has a "sense of justice, understanding".

The so-called fourth period is school age, which is characterized by the ability to achieve goals, the desire for success and productivity. Its most important value is performance and efficiency. In this age period, a lack of positive qualities, a lack of intelligence in solving problems, backwardness in assimilation of knowledge, etc. are also manifested. In the same period, a person begins to form an individual attitude to work.

The fifth period - spiritualism - is characterized by unique qualities, personality and an acute difference with other people. He also has flaws like self-doubt, self-doubt, self-doubt. The most important feature of this period is that "delay" is a change, and it has made some progress.

The sixth period - youth is characterized by the emergence of ability (ability) and the need for psychological rapprochement with another person (gender). Sexual orientation occupies a special place in this area. In addition, youth is distinguished by such qualities as loneliness and humanity.

The seventh period is a period of maturity, when a sense of productivity in all spheres of life and activity (in work, creativity, care, pinkness, transfer of experience, etc.) continuously accompanies it and serves as an impetus for the implementation of good intentions. In addition, it is possible that in this period, in some aspects, the established sense of "glasnost" will prevail as vicious.

The eighth period, that is, old age, is characterized by the fact that a person "copes with his duty, is satisfied and satisfied with his life." At this age, it's appropriate to talk about feelings of frustration and frustration. Wisdom, purity, sin-free separation is the most important component of the generosity of people of this age, which means that the attitude to each individual case from the point of view of personality and community is their highest strength. In his work "Psychology of Alcohol," E. Spranger recommends the inclusion of girls aged 13 to 19 years, and young men - from 14 to 22 years. According to E. Spranger, the main changes occurring at this age are:

- a) detection of personal "I";
- b) increased reflex;
- c) awareness of their individuality and recognition of personal qualities;
- d) appearance of life plans of good;
- e) being aware of your personal life, etc. He believes that the crisis between the ages of 14

and 17 gives them a sense of child care. Another feature of 17-21 youth is the emergence of a "crisis" and feelings of loneliness surrounded by peers and society. This creates historically conditioned conditions and factors.

E. Spranger, K. Buhler, A. Maslow and others are major representatives of personological theory.

Among the founders of the cognitive trend were J. Piaget. You can enter Kelly and others.

J. Piaget's theory of intelligence is divided into two important aspects: the study of functions of intelligence and periods of intelligence. The main functions of intelligence are organization (orderliness) and adaptation (adaptation, adaptation), which are called functional invariance of intelligence.

The author divides the development of intelligence in personality into the following stages: sensory intelligence (from birth to age 2);

preoperative thinking period (2 to 7 years);

the period of specific operations (from 7-8 to 11-12 years);

period of formal (official) operations.

The cognitive genetic theory includes a group of psychologists who continued the ideas of J. Piaget. L. Colberg, D. Bromley, J. Birrer, A. Wallon, G. Grimm.

French psychologist A. Vallon believes that personality development is divided into the following stages:

gestation in utero;

period of impulsive action - from birth to 6 months;

emotional (emotional) period - from 6 months to 1 year;

sensorimotor period (combination of perception and movement) - from 1 to 3 years;

period of personalism (transformation) - from 3 to 5 years;

differentiation period - from 6 to 11 years;

7) the period of puberty and alcoholism - from 12 to 18 years. Another major French psychologist, Zazzo, advises, based on the principles of education and upbringing at home, to approach this problem differently and interpret it so that it can be divided into the following stages:

The first stage is from birth to 3 years.

The second stage is from 3 to 6 years.

The third stage is from 6 to 9 years.

The fourth stage is from 9 to 12 years.

The fifth stage is from 12 to 15 years.

The sixth stage is from 15 to 18 years old.

It follows from the scheme that R. Zazzo's approach to the stages of personality development, based on the theory of formation, improvement as an individual, led to the limitation of the upper limit of personality formation, that is, to its socialization. Therefore, his teaching does not allow us to reflect on how a person is improved, changed, developed and legal.

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